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An overview of basic Counselling Services in Child Care Institutes (CCIs) in Kamrup Metro District, Guwahati, Assam

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Abstract

According to Mission Vatsalya Implementation Guidelines Child Care Institutes based on the Juvenile Justice (Care and Protection of Children) Act, 2015 empowers the State Government either by itself or in collaboration with voluntary organizations to set up homes in every district for the reception and residential care of Children in need of Care and Protection (CNCP) and Children in Conflict with Law (CCL). These CCIs shall serve as a home away from home and provide comprehensive child care facilities to children for their all-round development till the children's social re-integration through non-institutional care. They shall work towards enhancing the capacities and skills of children and work with their families with the view of facilitating their reintegration and rehabilitation into mainstream society. The mission shall support the different types of CCIs in the districts like Child Care Institutions for Children in Need of Care and Protection, Special Unit for Children with Special Needs, Open Shelters, Specialized Adoption Agencies (SAA) etc. The children who are come to the CCIs are belonged to the different categories like child labour, child marriage, child trafficking, orphan, abandoned etc. The children have come along with their traumatic situation. In this situation it is a big question who will provide them the mental support, proper guidance to overcome their trauma, in CCIs the counsellors are playing the main role to provide the counselling service to the needy children to handle the mental situation properly with dignity. Thus this study is conducted to know the basic Counselling services in CCIS in Kamrup Metro District, Guwahati, Assam and try to highlight some valuable findings for strengthening the counselling services. This paper tries to examine the basic services and issues facing while provide counselling services with a quantitative study among the counsellors with purposive sampling method in the CCIs of Kamrup Metro District for study. Data are collected with quantitative method by using selfmade interview schedule questionnaire. The paper concludes with a study of valuable suggestion to overcome the issues with positive outcome.

Keywords: *Child Care Institutes, Counselor, Children*

Introduction

According to UNICEF's counselling is defined as an inter-personal, interactive process between a service provider and an individual or family that goes beyond simple information delivery to facilitate mutual communication, support and collaborative decision-making to achieve positive behavioral changes and address social, emotional, or health-related issues. It involves using communication skills to create a safe, trusting environment where people can explore their challenges, understand their needs and develop solutions to improve their well-being and manage their lives.

Key Aspects of UNICEF's Approach to Counselling:

- It's an Interactive Relationship,
- Relationship Based,
- Problem-Solving focused,
- Behavioral Change,
- Holistic Support,
- Empowering Decision-Making.

Counselor is playing a vital role in the CCIs through their good practices. As the children are staying in the Children Home already faced a traumatic challenging life situation, it is not possible to overcome without empathy. Counselor has the capacity to deal with empathy with non judgemental attitude among the deprived children. In a Children Home without counselling is like a library without book. A counselor can provide them the psychosocial services so that the children are able to understand what is right and after that take decision independently in a proper way.

In every Child Care Institute there is a counselor who is professionally trained. As per Mission Vatsalya Guidelines the counsellor is providing the various services for the inmates of the CCIs to handle the life situation in a positive way. While providing the services the counselors are also facing some challenges in the CCIs. The counselors are eligible to look after the every psychosocial aspect of children with following the ethical principles of counselling. The recommendation mentioned in the counselling report is also important to take further decision of a child by the Child Welfare Committee (CWC). It is important to take care of the services which is delivered by the counselor for the best interest of the children.

Category of the children in CCIs:

As we all are aware that below the age of 18 years we called it child. In our daily life of the children and the children of the CCIs life experience are totally different. In the early age of the children of Children Home are already suffering from trauma as like some are victim of child labour, victim of child marriage, victim of sexually abuse, victim of trafficking etc. In a single word it is very difficult to understand their trauma with empathy. As per the order of Child welfare Committee the children are sheltered in a Children

Home as per JJ Act 2015. After that the concern counselors are responsible to provide the counselling services with empathy. So that the children are able to cope up with their traumatic situation in a positive way and which will lead a meaningful life.

Significance of the study:

The problem has identified to study the basic services of Counselling in Child Care Institutes in Kamrup Metro district, Guwahati Assam for better understanding the service of the counselling. Mostly the children of Children Home are deprived from their fundamental rights and they are the victim of different categories like child marriage, child labour, abuse, orphan etc. for the best interest of the children as per JJ Act 2015 the counselling is introduced in the CCIs to overcome the trauma of the needy children.

Generally, the counselling is applicable for the children who are deprived from their rights of a life. Through the counselling guidance children are aware about their rights and make them eligible to understand their needs, rights and take a stand independently. The counselling services provide an positive attitude among the inmates of the Children Home to establish their self-esteem, self-recognition in future life situation.

Counselling is not a advice, it is a proper guidance where the children understand the different aspects of life through the self-awareness counselling session. For the best interest of the children counselling is demanding. To provide the service smoothly there is also some challenges facing the counselors of CCIs while providing the service in some areas. For the better understanding of the service the researcher is trying to conduct this study to know the basic services of counselling in the Child Care Institutes in Kamrup Metro District, Guwahati, Assam.

Statement of the problem:

Keeping in mind the need and significance of the study, the paper is introduced as:

An overview of basic Counselling Services in Child Care Institutes (CCIs) in Kamrup Metro District, Guwahati, Assam

Objectives of the study:

- To know the basic services of counselling in Kamrup Metro District Guwahati with reference to CCI,
- To analyse the issues facing while provide counselling,
- To suggest some measures for the better services of counselling in CCIs.

Design of the study:

Method of the study:

The present study is survey research conducted on Child Care Institutes, in the Kamrup Metro District of Guwahati, Assam. In this study researcher tries to understand the services of counselling in the CCIs and try to make a complete picture from the study.

Sample:

Population for the study is counsellor of CCI. In this study researcher selected 20 sample of CCI centre

which is situated in the Guwahati with the help of purposive sampling method. The data are collected from the concern staff. The CCI are selected on a purpose. Kamrup Metro district is select for the study as the all over Assam the highest CCI is available in the Guwahati. The more resources are available than the other district.

Tools of data collection:

Researcher collected the information on various ground in the CCI with the help of semi structured interview schedule, direct observation of the counselor to help the researcher to find the valuable findings about the service of counselling. Quantitative method is used for data collection and analysed it with tabulation, graph to give a picture of the result.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

Quantitative data was collected to know the status of the service of counselling in a systematic manner.

Counsellors attitude on Counselling service:

It was observed that the counsellors showed positive response in the service of counselling in the district of Kamrup Metro the CCI of Govt and NGO run, Guwahati, Assam.

There are some general information about the Counselling Service:

Dimension	Responses (In Key words)	Positive Result %	Negative/Others%
Home District	Kamrup Metro	90%	10% others
Age	20-30 30-40	30% (20-30 age group) 70% (30-40) age group	
Relationship	Single Married	Married 70%	30% Single
Educational Qualifications	BSC/MAS TER	90% master degree	10% BSC
Employment	CCI type GOVT/NGO	80% NGO	20% GOVT
Working experience	10 years Below 10 Years	50% 10 years +	50% below 10 years
Training	5 times More than 10 times	70% 5 times	30% 10 times

Table 1: General information about the counsellor of the Child Care Institutes (CCIs):

Analyse of general service of counselling status in Child Care Institutes (CCIs):

Facility	Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Strongly Disagree	Disagree
Counselling room	90%	10%	0%	0%	0%
Trained personnel	100%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Individual Counselling	90%	10%	0%	0%	0%
Group Counselling	50%	50%	0%	0%	0%
Career Counselling	0%	90%	10%	0%	0%
Family Counselling	0%	50%	50%	0%	0%
Health Issues Counselling	0%	100%	0%	0%	0%

Table 2: General Counselling service status of Child Care Institutes CCIs - Graph

In this analysed found 90% respond strongly agreed about counselling room, 10% agreed, 100% strongly agreed about trained personnel, 90% showed strongly agreed about individual Counselling and 10% agreed, 50% strongly agreed about group counselling and 50% agreed about, 90% agreed about career counselling and 10% responded neutral, 50% agreed about family counselling and 50% responded neutrally, 100% responded positively about health counselling.

Ethical principles of Counselling practiced in Child Care Institutes (CCIs):

Ethical Principles of Counselling	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Strongly Disagree	Disagree
Competence	100%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Trustworthy	100%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Honesty	100%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Confidentiality	100%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Respectfulness	0%	100%	0%	0%	0%

Table 3: Ethical principles of Counselling practiced in Child Care Institutes CCIs

Graph

In this analysed found all the area of Ethical principles of Counselling like Competence, trustworthy, honesty, confidentiality, respectfulness respond strongly agreed 100%.

Issues Dealt with Counselling in Child Care Institutes (CCIs):

Issues	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Strongly Disagree	Disagree
Socialization issues	60%	0%	0%	40%	0%
Interpersonal Relation Issues	0%	60%	0%	40%	0%

Communication Issues	0%	50%	0%	50%	0%
Self-Harm Issues	60%	0%	0%	40%	0%
Family Related Issues	80%	0%	20%	0%	0%
Career Related Issues	0%	50%	0%	0%	50%
Peer Related Issues	50%	0%	50%	0%	0%
Administrative Issues	80%	10%	10%	0%	0%

Table 4: Status of issues dealt with counselling in Child Care Institutes CCIs

In this analysed found 60% strongly agreed about socialization issues, 40% strongly disagree, 60% respond positively about interpersonal relationship issues, 40% respond negatively, 50% respond agree about communication issues and 50% strongly disagreed, 60% respond strongly agreed about self harm and 40% strongly disagree, 80% respond family related issues and 20% respond neutrally, 50% agreed career related issues and 50% disagreed, 50% strongly agreed peer related issues and 50% respond neutrally, 80% respond strongly agreed about administrative issues and 10% agreed, 10% found neutral.

Graph

Expectations by the staff member:

It was found that the counselors are positive about the affect of counselling in a Child Care Institutes. For the better service of Counselling Counselor expect some administrative support from their concern line

department as sometimes they are unable to fulfill their objectives properly due to lack of financial support, infrastructure facility, professional etc.

The findings of the study are discussed below:

1. The study was found that there is no provision for special psychologist for special case, needs to appoint psychologist permanently for better service of Counselling.
2. It was found that there is no separate Counsellor for different area like career counsellor, health Counsellor, relationship Counsellor for the quality service of Counselling.
3. It was found that lack of awareness about Counselling service among the others staff, needs awareness more on the area of Counselling.
4. It was found that the salary of the counsellor is not sufficient based on their experience, lack of others facilities like health insurance etc, needs to proper monitor by the concern official.
5. It was found that lack of therapy material, needs to added more material for better service of Counselling.

Suggestions and discussion:

The Counselling is a service where the victim children of the Child Care Institutes are able to overcome their trauma with proper guidance by the Counsellor of Children Home with the help of proper services. There is a big question in our mind that what are the services provided by the counselor in the present time of the CCIs in Kamrup Metro district. In this study, it is analysed that the different areas are covered in the counselling services with positivity among the Children of Children Home like family Counselling, group Counselling, Individual Counselling, Career Counselling, Health and other Counselling with following the ethical principles. While provide Counselling there are some issues faced by the concern Counsellor like Interpersonal Issues, Peer related issues, Self-Harm issues, Administrative Issues etc. To overcome the challenges there is some additional support needed to fulfilling the main objectives of the Counselling Services properly for the best interest of the Children.

There are some suggestions to overcome the challenges:

1. Every human being deserved appreciation, it will be very effective if create a platform of children in yearly basis where the best practice will be awarded in a common platform in all over Assam, so that other deprived Children will motivate easily along with the Counsellors also.
2. We all are know that without proper awareness every work is challenging, it will be very thankfull if the concern official will highly focus on awareness program about Counselling Service in a systematic approach in grassroot level through some creative ideas and adult learning approach

like drama play, game therapy, etc instead of traditional teaching approach. So that the service holders are easily performed their role in a smooth manner.

3. We all are know that for quality service needs specific staff, it will be highly encouraged if area wise counsellor will appoint by the concern official like Career Counsellor, Psychologist, Health Counsellor etc, it will help the present Counsellor and decreased their workload.
4. In modern life circle it is impossible to survive without the minimum facility, it will be encouragible if the concern department will look into the other facilities of the staff for encouragement based on their experience, qualification like health insurance, scale pay benefit, mobile bill etc.

Conclusion:

The life of the children of Children Home are not so easy as they are the victim of any kind of abuse. This kind of children's shelter are the main focus of a Children Home as they are the children in need of care and protection. As per Juvenile Justice Care and Protection Act 2015 the all rules followed accordingly in a CCI. Counsellors are also the main role in a CCI to give a proper guidance among the victim children in a positive manner so that they will lead a self sufficient life with dignity. In this study it came to know that the Counsellor are trying their best to give proper Counselling Service in a Children home, but due to some challenges they are facing some difficulty to fulfill their objectives properly. We all know where is a will there is a way so with proper constant monitoring, follow up by the respected official will help to lead a better quality service in future life.

Lastly "Failures comes only when we forget our ideals and objectives and principles"

- Jawaharlal Nehru

References:

1. Government of India. (2015). *The Juvenile Justice (Care and Protection of Children) Act, 2015*. Ministry of Law and Justice.
2. Ministry of Women and Child Development. (2022, July 5). *Mission Vatsalya implementation guidelines*. Government of India.

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